

Simultaneous Estimation of MIRABEGRON AND SILODOSIN Using First Order Derivative Spectroscopic Method and Dual Wavelength Method

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Abstract: A simple, rapid, precise, accurate, economical and reproducible UV method was developed and validated for the determination of Mirabegron (MIRA) and Silodosin (SILO) which was used in combined ratio of (1: 1.25) for treatment of patient suffering with Heart Failure.^[1] Two precise, accurate and economical UV spectrophotometric (First Order Derivative Method and Dual Wavelength Method) were developed and validated for Quantitative determination of Mirabegron and Silodosin. The First Order Derivative Spectroscopic Method and Dual Wavelength Method for MIRA and SILO were found to be linear over the range of 15- 25 µg/ml and 4.8-11.2 µg/ml respectively. The estimation of MIRA was done at ZCP of MIRA (221.7 nm) and SILO was done at the ZCP of SILO (269.5 nm) in first order derivative spectroscopic method. The absorbance difference was measured between the wavelength range of 215.3 – 230 nm and 269.5 – 273 nm for MIRA and SILO respectively in Dual Wavelength Method. Both the methods were validated as per ICH guideline.

Keywords: Mirabegron, Silodosin, UV Spectroscopy, First order derivative method, Dual wavelength method

I. INTRODUCTION:

Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH), sometimes referred to as benign prostatic enlargement (BPE), is a frequent cause of bladder out flow obstruction (BOO) and is one of the most common diseases to affect men beyond middle age.. Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) is a disorder in which the prostate, a walnut-sized organ made up of glandular and muscle tissue, enlarges. Part of the urethra, the tube that transports urine and sperm out of the body, is surrounded by the prostate. Directly beneath the bladder and in front of the rectum is the prostate. Because the urethra goes through the prostate, an enlarged prostate can prevent urine or sperm from passing through the urethra.^(1,2)

A. Mirabegron (MIRA):

Mirabegron (MIRA) is chemically known as 2-(2-amino-1,3-thiazol-4-yl)-N-[4-[2-[(2R)-2-hydroxy-2-phenylethyl] amino] ethyl] phenyl] acetamide with Molecular Formula and Molecular Weight, C₂₁H₂₄N₄O₂S and 396.506 gm/mole respectively belonging to the Beta-3 adrenergic agonists, shown in Fig.1. This API is freely soluble in Ethanol. MOA of this drug is, During the storage phase of the urine bladder fill-void cycle, the activation of beta-3 receptors relaxes the detrusor smooth muscle, increasing the bladder's storage capacity and reducing frequency and feelings of urgency.^[1,4]

B. Silodosin (SILO):

Silodosin (SILO) is chemically known as 1-(3-hydroxypropyl)-5-[(2R)-({2-[2-[2-(2,2,2-trifluoromethoxy)phenoxy]ethyl]amino)propyl]in doline-7-carboxamide with Molecular Formula and

Molecular Weight $C_{25}H_{32}F_3N_3O_4$ and 495.53gm/mole respectively belonging to the Alpha Blockers category, shown in Fig. 2. This API is slightly soluble in Water and soluble in Methanol. MOA of this drug is, Silodosin is blocks the post synaptic alpha-1 adrenoreceptors found in the human prostate, bladder base, bladder neck, prostatic capsule, and prostatic urethra. The smooth muscles in these tissues may relax when these alpha-1 adrenoreceptors are blocked, which will enhance urine flow and lessen BPH (benign prostatic hyperplasia) symptoms. [3-4]

Fig.1 Chemical Structure of MIRA

Fig. 2 Chemical Structure of SILO

A study of the Literature Review on Analytical Method Development and Validation for Mirabegron and Silodosin, it was found that though several analytical techniques have been developed for each medication alone or in combination with other drugs [5-24], as far as we are aware, there is no published simultaneous procedure for their determination. In this communication, we present a new, quick, accurate, and simple UV-spectrophotometric method for determining Mirabegron and Silodosin simultaneously. Thus, there is a scope to Develop and Validate Spectrophotometric techniques for the combination of Mirabegron and Silodosin in compliance with ICH Q2(R2) specifications.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A. Instruments:

A double-beam UV-visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu1900 i) and two matched quartz cells (1-cm) were utilized for recording the absorbance of the solution.

B. Chemicals:

Materials and solvents:

Mirabegron and Silodosin were procured as samples from Merrill Pharma Pvt. Ltd., Modasar, Bavla, Gujarat. Methanol (HPLC grade), Acetonitrile (HPLC grade), Water (HPLC grade) – Rankem

Ortho Phosphoric Acid (HPLC grade) – Thomas baker

III. PREPARATION OF STANDARD SOLUTION:

Accurately weighed 10 mg of Mirabegron and Silodosin were dissolved in 10 mL methanol in volumetric flasks to obtain a solution concentration as 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. About 1-mL aliquot from this was diluted 10 mL with methanol in a volumetric flask to obtain 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ solution. From these, further dilutions were made so as to obtain solution ranges from 25 to 15 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 4.8 to 11.2 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for MIRA and SILO respectively.

A. Preparation of Sample Solution:

Withdraw 2.5 mL and 2 mL from the mid-stock solution of Mirabegron and Silodosin in 10 mL volumetric flask with methanol to give a solution containing 25 µg/ml and 8.0 µg/ml of MIRA and SILO and measure the absorbance (Figure 3).

Fig.3 Overlay Spectra of MIRA and SILO

Selection Of Wavelength:

1. For First order derivative method:

- Aliquots of 2.5 ml from working stock solution of MIRA (100 µg/ml) 2.0 ml from working stock solution of SILO (100 µg/ml) and were pipette out and taken into two separate volumetric flasks of 10 ml and 25 ml volume was made up to mark with methanol to give a solution containing 25 µg/ml and 8.0 µg/ml of MIRA and SILO. Each solution was scanned between 200-400 nm against method as blank. The zero order spectra data was processed to obtain first order derivative spectrum in the range of 400-200 nm. In First order spectra Zero Crossing Point of MIRA at 221.7 nm and Zero Crossing point of SILO at 269.5 nm. Wavelength selected for Quantitation were 269.5 nm for MIRA (ZCP of SILO) and 221.7 nm for SILO (ZCP of MIRA).

2. For Dual Wavelength Method:

- Aliquots of 2.5 ml from working stock solution of MIRA (100 µg/ml) 2.0 ml from working stock solution of SILO (100 µg/ml) and were pipette out and taken into two separate volumetric flasks of 10 ml and 25 ml volume was made up to mark with methanol to give a solution containing 25 µg/ml and 8.0 µg/ml of MIRA and SILO. The absorption spectra obtained showed absorption maxima at 249 nm for MIRA and 269 nm for SILO and the absorbance difference was measured between the wavelength range of 215.30 nm and 230.00 nm for MIRA and 265.50 nm and 273.00 nm for SILO.

Fig.4 Dual wavelength spectra of MIRA 5-15 µg/ml and SILO 4.8-11.2 µg/ml at wavelength 215.30 & 230.00 nm

Fig.5 Dual wavelength spectra of SILO 4.8-11.2 µg/ml and MIRA 5-15 µg/ml at wavelength 265.50-273.00 nm

IV.RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

A. First order derivative method:

1.Linearity :

Dilutions were made for a linearity range of 25-15 µg/mL for Mirabegron and 4.8-11.2 µg/mL for Silodosin. The regression coefficient was found to be in the range (Table 1). The calibration curve of Mirabegron and Silodosin is displayed in (Figure 4 and Figure 5).

Fig.6 Calibration curve for MIRA at 269.50 nm

Fig.7 Calibration curve for SILO at 221.70 nm

Table I. Linearity and range data of Mirabegron and Silodosin

Sr. No.	Parameters	MIRA	SILO
1	Linearity range (µg/mL)	15-35 µg/mL	4.8-11.2 µg/mL
2	Regression equation	$y = 0.0021x + 0.0023$	$y = 0.0009x + 0.0017$
3	Correlation coefficient	0.9991	0.9998

2. Precision:

Analysis was performed by carrying out repeatability studies (Table 2), inter-day and intra-day precision studies (Table 3 and 4). According per the methodology, the solutions were made, and absorbance values were measured. The precision of the method was confirmed from the % RSD value which was < 2% for Mirabegron and Silodosin.

Table II. Repeatability data of Mirabegron and Silodosin

Sr. No.	Drugs	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Mean \pm S.D	%RSD
1	MIRA	25	0.0544 \pm 0.0001	0.4860
2	SILO	8	0.0094 \pm 0.00008	0.8624

Table III. % Purity of drug of Intra-day precision

Sr. No.	Name of drug	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	%Purity of drug	%RSD
1	MIRA	20	99.58	0.5741
		25	99.89	0.4863
		30	100.12	0.4580
2	SILO	6.4	99.78	1.2820
		8	100.10	0.8638
		9.6	99.60	0.9259

Table IV. % Purity of drug of Inter-day precision

Sr. No.	Name of drug	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	%Purity of drug	%RSD
1	MIRA	20	99.12	0.8988
		25	99.02	0.7325
		30	99.89	0.6051
2	SILO	6.4	99.40	1.3638
		8	99.82	1.1585
		9.6	99.21	0.9983

3. Accuracy:

Accuracy The accuracy of the developed method was confirmed by a recovery study at three different concentrations (80%, 100%, and 120%). The % recovery at 80%, 100% and 120% for Mirabegron was found to be 99.66, 99.83, and 101.36% respectively and for Silodosin was found to be 100.69, 100.62, and 101.52 % respectively and is within the acceptable range of 95%-105%. The % RSD for Mirabegron and Silodosin was found to be < 2%. Hence, the method developed was accurate (Table 5).

Table V. Percentage recovery of added substances

Name of drug	% of drug	% percentage recovery	%RSD
MIRA	80	99.66	1.029
	100	99.83	
	120	101.36	
SILO	80	100.69	1.308
	100	100.62	
	120	101.52	

4. Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ):

The slope and standard deviation of the calibration curve were used to determine LOD and LOQ. The developed method was found to be sensitive as seen in Table 6.

Table VI. Percentage recovery of added substances

DRUG	LOD	LOQ
MIRA	0.170	0.516
SILO	0.175	0.531

5. Assay:

The above validated method can be employed to estimate Mirabegron and Silodosin in combined dosage form. According to the methodology the solutions were made and absorbance values measured at predetermined wavelengths. The results of Mirabegron and Silodosin were comparable with the corresponding labelled levels of marketed formulation and % assay was found to be 99.60 % for Mirabegron and 99.37 % for Silodosin which was within the acceptable limit (95%-105%) (Table 7)

Table VII. Results Of Assay

	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Amount obtain mean \pm S.D ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	%Assay of MIRA \pm S.D (n=3)	%Assay of SILO \pm S.D (n=3)
Synthetic Mixture	25	24.90 \pm 0.0725	99.60 \pm 0.2903	99.37 \pm 0.4301
	8	7.95 \pm 0.0207		

B. DUAL WAVELENGTH METHOD:

1. Linearity:

The linearity range for MIRA and SILO was found to be in the range of 15-25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 4.8-11.2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively.

Table VIII. Linearity data for MIRA at 265.50 & 273.00 nm and SILO at 215.30 & 230 nm.

Sr. No.	Parameters	MIRA	SILO
1	Linearity range (µg/mL)	15-35 µg/mL	4.8-11.2 µg/mL
2	Regression equation	$y = 0.0159x + 0.0175$	$y = 0.0177x + 0.0156$
3	Correlation coefficient	0.9996	0.9995

Fig 8. Calibration curve for MIRA at 265.50 and 273.00 nm

Fig.9 Calibration curve for SILO at 215.30 and 230.00 nm

2.Precision:

Analysis was performed by carrying out repeatability studies (Table 2), inter-day and intra-day precision studies which was < 2% for Mirabegron and Silodosin.

Table X: Repeatability data of Mirabegron and Silodosin

Sr. No.	Drugs	Concentration (µg/ml)	Mean ± S.D	%RSD
1	MIRA	25	0.4095 ± 0.0019	0.4655
2	SILO	8	0.1552 ± 0.0005	0.3829

Table XI. % Purity of drug of Intra-day and Inter-day precision

	Name of drug	Concentration (µg/mL)	%Purity of drug	%RSD
Intra day	MIRA	20	99.78	0.6329
		25	99.93	0.5117
		30	100.20	0.4023
	SILO	6.4	99.12	0.6771
		8	100.22	0.5157
		9.6	99.40	0.4051
Intraday	MIRA	20	99.60	0.7043
		25	99.58	0.6034
		30	100.12	0.5055
	SILO	6.4	99.08	0.7193
		8	100.16	0.6003
		9.6	99.20	0.5162

3.Accuracy:

Percentage recovery for MIRA and SILO at 265.50 nm & 273.00 nm and 215.30 nm & 230.00 nm were obtained, respectively. The result is depicted in table. Recovery was found to be in the limit of 98-102%

Table XII. % Recovery Data of Mirabegron and Silodosin.

Name of drug	% of drug	% percentage recovery	%RSD
MIRA	80	99.85	1.080
	100	100.83	
	120	101.27	
SILO	80	99.30	1.251
	100	99.68	
	120	101.04	

4. Assay:

The % assay was found to be 99.69 % for Mirabegron and 99.49 % for Silodosin which was within the acceptable limit (95%-105%).

Table XIII. Results Of Assay

Synthetic Mixture	Concentration (µg/ml)	Amount obtain mean ± S.D (µg/ml)	%Assay of MIRA ± S.D (n=3)	%Assay of SILO ± S.D (n=3)
	25	24.92 ± 0.0502	99.69 ± 0.2011	99.49 ± 0.2926
	8	7.96 ± 0.0234		

C. STATISTICAL COMPARISION OF DEVELOPMENT METHODS:

Statistical comparison of developed First order derivative method, Dual wavelength methods which were developed for simultaneous estimation of MIRA and SILO. To compare the developed method, ANOVA test was applied for assay by using Microsoft Excel- 2019 data analysis tool.

Table XIV. One way ANOVA test for development methods

METHODS		%MIRA	%SILO
First order derivative method		99.2	99.89
		99.56	99.15
		99.96	99.64
		99.52	98.78
		99.8	99.39
Dual wavelength method		99.4	99.62
		99.84	99.25
		99.68	99.75
		99.64	99.75
		99.92	99.125
SS	Between Group	0.034773	0.161303
	Within Group	0.5402	1.13124
df	Between Group	2	2
	Within Group	12	12
MS	Between Group	0.017387	0.080652
	Within Group	0.045017	0.09427
F Calculated		0.386227	0.855539
F Critical		3.885294	3.885294

Since, F Calculated was found to be less than F Calculated for both MIRA and SILO thus indicating that there is no significant difference observed in assay result among the three methods. Hence it was concluded that all three methods do not differ significantly.

V. CONCLUSION:

A. FIRST ORDER DERIVATIVE METHOD:

- Based on the result obtained from the analysis of MIRA and SILO in synthetic mixture using first order derivative method, it can be concluded that the method has linearity in the range of 15-35 µg/ml for MIRA and 4.8-11.2 µg/ml for SILO. The regression coefficient (R^2) was found to be 0.9991 and 0.9998 for MIRA and SILO respectively, and correlation coefficient (R) was found to be 0.9995 and 0.9999 for MIRA and SILO at 269.50 nm (ZCP of SILO) and 221.70 nm (ZCP of MIRA) respectively.
- Limit of detection for MIRA and SILO were found to be 0.1702 µg/ml and 0.1757 µg/ml and Limit of quantitation for MIRA and SILO were found to be 0.5162 µg/ml and 0.5315 µg/ml, respectively. The % assay was found to be 99.60 w/w and 99.37 %w/w for MIRA and SILO, respectively. Further %RSD was found to be less than 2% for repeatability, intraday and interday precision study.

B. DUAL WAVELENGTH METHOD:

- Based on the result obtained from the analysis of MIRA and SILO in synthetic mixture using first dual wavelength method, it can be concluded that the method has linearity in the range of 15-35 µg/ml for MIRA and 4.8-11.2 µg/ml for SILO. The regression coefficient (R^2) was found to be 0.9993 and 0.9991 for MIRA and SILO respectively, and correlation coefficient (R) was found to be 0.9996 and 0.9995 for MIRA and SILO at 215.30-230.00 nm and 265.50-273.00 nm.
- Limit of detection for MIRA and SILO were found to be 0.1702 µg/ml and 0.1752 µg/ml and Limit of quantitation for MIRA and SILO were found to be 0.5160 µg/ml and 0.5311 µg/ml respectively. The % assay was found to be 99.69 w/w and 99.49 %w/w for MIRA and SILO respectively. Further %RSD was found to be less than 2% for repeatability, intraday and interday precision study.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

The authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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